

National Journal of Hindi & Sanskrit Research

National Journal of Hindi & Sanskrit Research

Online, Peer Reviewed Journal, Impact Factor (RJIF): 5.11, ISSN NO. : 2454-9177

Publication Certificate

**This certificate confirms that “ Dr. Vinayak Bhat ” has published article titled
“ Principles of Partnership in Smriti Literature ”.**

Details of Published Article as follow:

Volume : 52

Issue : January - February

Year : 2024

Page No. : 42- 44

Yours Sincerely,

Anil Aggarwal

Publisher

National Journal of Hindi & Sanskrit Research

Web: www.sanskritarticle.com

National Journal of Hindi & Sanskrit Research

ISSN: 2454-9177

NJHSR 2024; 1(52): 42-44

© 2024 NJHSR

www.sanskritarticle.com

Dr. Vinayak Bhat

Research Scholar,

Department of Dharmashastra,

Karnataka Samskrit University,

Chamarajpete, Bangalore -560018

Principles of Partnership in Smriti Literature

Dr. Vinayak Bhat

Abstract:

The principles of partnership outlined in Smriti literature elucidate the essence of collaborative endeavors in ancient Indian society. Rooted in the Dharmashastra tradition, Vyavahāra serves as the cornerstone of legal procedures and dispute resolution mechanisms, guiding ethical conduct and equitable distribution. Sambhuya Samutthana, Brihaspati's insights, and Vyasa's teachings underscore the importance of integrity, competence, and shared responsibilities among partners. Yajnavalkya and Narada advocate for effective delegation, while Brihaspati emphasizes unanimous decision-making and accountability. Partners are collectively responsible for their actions, and misconduct warrants expulsion without entitlement to dividends. Upon dissolution, profits are divided equally among partners, reflecting fairness and equity. These principles encapsulate the enduring wisdom of ancient texts, fostering harmonious partnerships grounded in dharma and righteousness.

Key Words: Partnership, Smriti Literature, Ethics, Collaboration

Introduction:

Vyavahāra, an integral concept within Hindu law, forms the backbone of legal procedures and dispute resolution mechanisms. Rooted deeply in the Dharmashastra tradition, Vyavahāra finds profound significance in ancient Hindu texts, including the Smritis. Among the 18 renowned vyavahāras delineated in these texts, Sambhuya Samutthana stands out prominently. This particular vyavahāra emphasizes collaborative endeavors and collective efforts, reflecting the ethos of partnership and cooperation prevalent in ancient Indian society. Its prominence underscores the enduring relevance and timeless wisdom encapsulated within the ancient vyavahāras, offering invaluable insights into ethical conduct, equitable distribution, and harmonious interactions in various spheres of life.

Definition of Sambhuya Samutthana:

Sambhuya Samutthana embodies the collective endeavor of individuals from diverse professions – traders, actors, musicians, sculptors, farmers, and more – pooling their resources to embark on a common business venture or endeavor. As articulated by Narada, this collaborative effort is aimed at achieving mutual profit, with each participant sharing both the gains and losses in accordance with their investment.

Narada's definition underscores the essence of collaboration:

वणिक्प्रभृतयो यत्र कर्म सम्भूय कुर्वते।

तत्सम्भूय समुत्थानं व्यवहारपदं स्मृतम्॥¹

Correspondence:

Dr. Vinayak Bhat

Lecturer in Sanskrit, MES Prof.,

BR Subbarao PU College,

Vidyaranyaapura, Bangalore 97

Insights from Brihaspati Smriti :

Brihaspati, in his wisdom, accentuates the paramount importance of selecting partners endowed with noble character, skill, diligence, intelligence, financial acumen, and honesty. This selection ensures a harmonious collaboration wherein profits and losses are equitably distributed. Moreover, Brihaspati stresses the significance of integrity in all business dealings to maintain the sanctity of partnerships.

Manu's teachings echo:

राजा कर्मसु युक्तानां स्त्रीणां प्रेष्यजनस्य च।
प्रत्यहं कल्पयेद् वृत्तिं स्थानं कर्मानुरूपतः॥²

Guiding Principles of Conduct:

Vyasa, in his profound insights, emphasizes the pivotal role of integrity in business endeavors. Whether operating individually or in partnership, each partner must uphold honesty, diligence, and competence to ensure the ethical conduct of business affairs.

Brihaspati's words resonate deeply:

कुलीनदक्षानलसः प्राज्ञैर्नाणिकवेदिभिः।
आयव्ययज्ञैः शुचिभिः शूरैः कुर्यात्साहसक्रियाम्॥³

Division of Responsibilities:

According to the guidance of Yajnavalkya and Narada, partners must effectively delegate tasks to competent individuals within the partnership. If a partner finds themselves unable to execute a task, it should be entrusted to another capable individual to ensure the smooth functioning of operations.

Vyasa prescribe:

समक्षमसमक्षं वा अवञ्चयन्तः परस्परम्।
नानापण्यानुसारात्ते प्रकुर्युः क्रयविक्रयौ॥⁴

Shared Decision Making:

In accordance with the teachings of Brihaspati, decisions pertaining to property transactions must be unanimous among all partners. Any unilateral action, such as selling or exchanging property without consensus, undermines the collaborative spirit of the partnership and binds all partners to the consequences.

Brihaspati's counsel elucidates:

बहूनां सम्मतो यस्तु दद्यादेको धनं नरः।
करणं कारयेद्वापि सर्वैरपि कृतं भवेत्॥⁵

Responsibility and Liability:

Each partner within a partnership bears collective responsibility for the actions and decisions undertaken. If a partner's negligence or misconduct results in harm or loss, they must individually bear the consequences, as enshrined in the teachings of Smriti literature.

चोरतः सलिलादग्नेर्द्रयं यस्तु समाहरेत्।
तस्यांशो दशमो देयः सर्ववादेष्वायं विधिः॥⁶

Dismissal for Misconduct:

Partners found engaging in fraudulent activities or misconduct must face expulsion from the partnership without any claim to dividends, ensuring the integrity and sanctity of the partnership.

जिह्व त्यजेयुर्निर्लाभमशक्तोऽन्येन कारयेत्॥⁷

Succession and Inheritance:

Upon a partner's demise or departure, their share is inherited by their rightful heirs. Should no successors be identified, the remaining partners may acquire the share after a stipulated period, or it may revert to the king, as per the tenets of Smriti literature.

देशान्तरगते प्रेते द्रव्यं दायदबान्धवाः।

ज्ञातयो वा हरेयुस्तदागतास्तैर्विना नृपः॥⁸

Equal Division of Profits:

When the decision to dissolve the partnership arises, profits should be divided equitably among all partners, fostering fairness and equity in accordance with the guidance of Katyayana.

Katyayana's wisdom asserts:

समवेतास्तु ये केचिच्छिल्पिनो वणिजोऽपि वा।

अविभज्य पृथग्भूतैः प्राप्तं तत्र फलं समम्॥⁹

Conclusion:

The principles of partnership outlined in Smriti literature offer a comprehensive blueprint for fostering fair, ethical, and harmonious collaborations in business ventures. By emphasizing integrity, accountability, shared decision-making, and equitable distribution of profits and responsibilities, these principles uphold the sacred values of dharma and righteousness. Adherence to these guiding principles ensures the sustenance and prosperity of partnerships, laying the foundation for enduring success and mutual growth.

Reference Books

- Manusmriti, Dr. Urmila Rustagi, JP Publishing House Delhi
- Manusmriti, Ulluka Bhatta, Dr. Rakesh Shastri, Vidyanidhi Prakashan Delhi
- Narada Smriti , Maharshi University of Management Vedic Literature Collection
- Brihaspati Smriti , Maharshi University of Management Vedic Literature Collection
- Yajnavalkya Smriti, Nirnaya Sagar Press Mumbai 1941
- Katyayana Smriti, Manmatha Nath Dutt | 2006
- Smriti Chandrika , Devanna Bhatta, BiblioBazaar, LLC
- Vyavahara Mayukha, Bhatta Neelakantha , Published by Bhandarkar Oriental Research Institute, Poona1926

Reference

- ¹ Narada Smriti 6.07
- ² Manusmriti 7.125
- ³ Brihaspati Smriti, Smriti Chandrika II , Pg 84
- ⁴ Vyasa Smriti, Smriti Chandrika , Pg 185
- ⁵ Brihaspati Smriti, Vyavahara Mayukha Pg-200
- ⁶ Katyayana Smriti 631
- ⁷ Yajnavalkya Smriti 2.265
- ⁸ Yajnavalkya Smriti 2.264
- ⁹ Katyayana Smriti 624